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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The submillimeter is a crucial part of the electromagnetic spectrum for studies of the cold universe, essential to understand the origins of galaxies, and the physical and chemical conditions within the interstellar medium in the dense and cold molecular clouds in which stars and planetary systems form. A next generation of single dish telescopes are uniquely poised to deliver accurate measurements of fundamental astrophysical processes that govern stellar birth and evolution, galaxy formation, and the coming-of-age of the universe itself. The submillimeter regime is accessible in several atmospheric windows from the ground, where single dish telescopes are able to exploit a rapidly growing detector technology to implement powerful instruments which can survey vast regions of the sky to unprecedented depths. In this white paper we will discuss key research areas that require ground-based Submillimeter Wave observatories, exploiting the crucial submillimeter diagnostics of the molecular ISM, and the redshifted dust and strong ISM cooling lines from all galaxies at $z > 1$ – the first half of the history of our Universe, when galaxies were actively assembling and building their stellar populations. At the moment there are no submillimeter single dish telescopes funded in Canada. Those that Canadian astronomers use are funded through individual academic grants, or through external collaborations. This white paper will bring together discussions of the science cases, and descriptions of the proposed facilities, along with prospects for Canadian involvement and timelines of single dish mm/submm facilities: CCAT-prime, JCMT upgrades, APEX upgrades, SPT, ACT, Polarbear, Simon's Observatory, CCAT-25, and AtLAST.

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LRP2020 White Paper

Science with Ground-based, Single-dish Submillimeter-wave Telescopes

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1 Introduction

Submillimetre/millimetre (SMM) wavelengths are a key and unique window into our cosmic origins, the architecture of the Universe and structures within it on all scales. The cosmic microwave background, starburst galaxies over cosmic time, star-forming regions, and debris disks, have all had their secrets unlocked through SMM observations. From the discovery of dusty sub-mm galaxies in the early Universe through to the ringed nature of protostellar disks, our understanding of the formation, destruction, and evolution of objects in the Universe has and will continue to require a comprehensive view of the sub-mm sky. What was once seen as a niche science area with limited technological capabilities has become a mature field. SMM observations are now a crucial component of essentially all sub-areas of astronomy, and are supported by a suite of facilities with complementary strengths. The submillimeter regime is accessible in several atmospheric windows from the ground, where single-dish telescopes are able to exploit a rapidly growing detector technology to implement powerful instruments that can survey vast regions of the sky to unprecedented depths.

Canada holds a long history of excellence and expertise in SMM astronomy, supported not only through continued access to cutting-edge facilities, but by strong involvement at the end-to-end science level. The current generation single-dish sub-mm facilities have given a glimpse of the potential for discovery, while sub-mm interferometers have presented a high-resolution view into the finer details of regions/objects. However, our understanding of structure formation and our full use of these interferometers is now hampered by the limited sensitivity of our sub-mm view of the Universe at larger scales. We must continue to invest in SMM facilities at a level that allows Canadians to maintain our position as a world-leader in an important area of science. Historically, Canadians have enjoyed access to the largest, best-equipped SMM single-dish in the world (namely JCMT). Without such continued access, Canadian scientists will lack a key facility for the study of the SMM Universe – one fundamental to their future success with ALMA.

The James Clerk Maxwell Telescope (JCMT) and the Cerro Chajnantor Atacama Telescope-prime (CCAT-p), open to any Canadian astronomer, represent the two key SMM single-dish telescope projects in which Canada continues to pursue leadership and involvement. In addition, several cosmic microwave background (CMB) focused experiments (ACT, BICEP/Keck, POLARBEAR, SPT, Simons Observatory) offer a subset of Canadians a further opportunity to investigate the SMM sky, over a range of topics even beyond the CMB and cosmology.

However, Canada has officially withdrawn from the James Clerk Maxwell Telescope since 2015, when the East Asian Observatory took over operations. While a grassroots university effort has found a minimum of funds to continue a modest involvement (at the \sim \$150k/yr level), these channels have now dried up as well, and this on the eve of a major telescope and instrumentation upgrade plan. A CFI proposal will be submitted in January 2020 (PI: C. Wilson) by a combination of McMaster, UBC, U. Manitoba, U. Montreal, and Queen's to fund an involvement in the development of the new bolometer camera to succeed SCUBA-2.

While the 25-m CCAT, JCMT's obvious successor, was highly endorsed in the US 2010 decadal review, it was put on hold due to a lack of funds in the US. A pathfinder to CCAT-25, to exploit the extremely good site of the CCAT Observatory, was proposed in 2016, and the 6-m CCAT-prime (CCAT-p) is now under construction with first light planned in 2023. Canadian astronomers, again through a multi-university consortium, have maintained involvement and helped shape the direction of CCAT-p, but the current lack of Canadian funding for CCAT-p has

also left the Canadian astronomy community at a critical cross-roads. A CFI proposal will be submitted in January 2020 (PI: M. Fich) by U. Alberta, UBC, U.Toronto, and U.Waterloo to fund a partnership in CCAT-p, providing funds for building observatory infrastructure and assembling and commissioning the telescope in Chile and to build its key survey camera at short wavelengths, the “pCam350”. Researchers at other Canadian institutions are also involved with both instrumental and scientific work with CCAT-p.

1.1 New science enabled by single-dish SMM

Existing and planned single-dish SMM telescopes fill a crucial role in wider field mapping as *survey machines* and “finder” telescopes for sources to be followed up with interferometers like ALMA, SMA, and NOEMA. This cannot be overstated, as these interferometers are simply far too slow (fields of view, FoVs, too small) to map regions on the sky to suitable depths to find objects of interest to follow up. However, SMM single-dishes also pioneer new science directions; in some cases, these science cases are completely out of reach for interferometers with their very limited mapping capabilities.

An example is the Transient Survey initiated on JCMT (Herczeg et al., 2017) which has opened up an entirely new field of scientific research: the study of time-variable phenomena at submillimetre wavelengths. This research is aimed at deriving a detailed description of the variable accretion rate onto young protostars in order to better estimate protostellar lifetimes and to work towards a physical description of the inner circumstellar disk, which is the site of planet formation. The Transient Survey has detected the first submillimetre protostellar transients (Mairs et al., 2017), including the brightest stellar flare ever detected (Mairs et al., 2019). Another science breakthrough in SMM transients has been the submm emission in afterglows from GRBs (the first detection of a submm GRB afterglow was made by Canadians using the JCMT (Fich et al., 2001). There are now many papers on this topic and the Greenland telescope has this as a focus of their work. CCAT-p will cover the southern half of the sky, and its incredible mapping speed will open a new phase space for other transients, much as LSST will transform optical transient studies.

In the distant Universe, new classes of objects are routinely discovered through single-dish wide-field surveys, although typically requiring extensive interferometric follow up to fully understand the detailed properties. A recent example is very high redshift protoclusters of galaxies ($z > 4$), with the key discovery that massive structures in the early Universe undergo a sort of inside-out, early collapse, leading to bright concentrated bursts of star formation in dense cores. Surveys with JCMT, SPT, APEX, and Herschel (single-dish wide-field maps) have uncovered several examples (Miller et al., 2018; Oteo et al., 2018).

SMM polarization maps on single-dish facilities (see below for JCMT/POL-2) represent the uncovering of another important new direction in SMM science.

2 Existing and Planned Facilities

The JCMT maintains a world leadership role in the field of single-dish SMM astronomy. Recent advances include continuum polarization mapping with SCUBA-2/POL-2 emerging as a unique and highly oversubscribed facility, opening up an untapped discovery space in magnetic turbulence in star formation (Pattle et al., 2019). POL-2 was a Canadian-led instrument (PI: P. Bastien). At short $<450\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ wavelengths, while the Mauna Kea site is somewhat limiting compared to higher sites in the Atacama, there is no doubt that deep SCUBA-2 maps have claimed a unique and powerful capability, despite the small sizes of these deep fields (Geach et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2017). The mainstay wide-field and deep surveys at $850\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ using SCUBA-2, in extragalactic (e.g., Geach et al. 2017), star formation (e.g., Eden et al. 2019), and nearby galaxies (e.g., Smith et al. 2019), have enabled a wide range of transformative science, leading to large ALMA allocations for follow up, and spectacular, often paradigm-shifting results (see ALMA WP – C. Wilson et al., for examples).

CCAT-p is a facility aimed at exploiting the superb atmospheric transmission at short wavelengths on Cerro Chajnantor to gain a leap in sensitivity and areal coverage at the poorly studied $350\text{--}200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ windows. While the aperture is modest (6 m), the novel ultra-wide-field telescope design and recent advances in detector technology will allow for transformational $350\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ surveys. The same wide-field mapping and detector counts will also permit

simultaneous mapping at longer wavelengths, crucial for cosmological science cases, and filling a niche at these wavelengths in survey speed.

The natural extension to CCAT-p in the future will be a large aperture (25-m) version – CCAT, and at longer wavelengths, the Atacama Large Aperture Submillimeter Telescope (AtLAST – e.g., Klaassen et al. 2019), a concept for a 50-m class single-dish telescope at lower elevation (near the APEX site). While both of these projects are further in the future, probably not to begin construction before 2030, they both provide opportunities for Canadians to be involved from the earliest stages of project development during the 2020 to 2030 period.

Also available to Canadians through international partnerships are the other key SMM single-dish facilities in operation, ESO’s APEX, the IRAM 30 m, and the 50-m Large Millimeter Telescope (LMT) in Mexico with its upcoming TolTEC camera (> 1 mm). Canadians regularly lead significant programs on these facilities, despite their being only partially open to international proposals. APEX remains somewhat competitive with the JCMT, situated at an even better site, and similar though smaller aperture (12 m vs 15 m). When new planned instrumentation comes online (Artemis), it will compete with JCMT, but will not match the capabilities of the new JCMT continuum camera being planned. IRAM 30 m and LMT operate at longer wavelengths than JCMT, and cannot fulfill the $>$ degree-scale fields of view that CCAT and AtLAST would provide, but their sensitive mapping capabilities with new and advanced instrumentation (NIKA-2 and TolTEC, respectively) will push the field forward in the meantime.

2.1 CCAT-p and PCam

Prime-Cam (PCam), will be a powerful, first-light camera for CCAT-p. CCAT-p is a 6-m aperture submillimeter (submm) to millimeter (mm) wave telescope that is independently funded and being built by an international consortium led by Cornell University, seeing completion by 2023. PCam will enable unique observations that address pressing astrophysical questions, ranging from the physics of star formation to Big Bang cosmology. PCam will simultaneously cover five bands centre at 220–860 GHz (1.6 to 0.35 mm). The wavelength coverage, sensitivity, spatial resolution and large FoV of PCam on CCAT-p allow it to perform a set of wide-area surveys to uniquely address the following forefront scientific goals (see Fig. 1). **1.** Trace the formation and large-scale three-dimensional clustering of the first star-forming galaxies during the epoch of reionization through wide-field, broad-band spectroscopy (Kovetz et al., 2017). **2.** Constrain dark energy and feedback mechanisms by measuring the physical properties and distribution of galaxy clusters via the Sunyaev-Zeldovich (SZ) effects on the CMB (Mittal et al., 2017). **3.** Enable more precise constraints on inflationary gravity waves and light relics by measuring polarized CMB foregrounds and Rayleigh scattering (Alipour et al., 2015). **4.** Directly trace the evolution of dusty-obscured star formation in galaxies since the epoch of galaxy assembly, starting >10 billion years ago (Riechers et al., 2013).

PCam will be built by Cornell, in collaboration with our Canadian university and NRC consortium, Stanford/SLAC and the University of Michigan. It will have three modules that are inserted into a single cryostat, each of which are optimized for wide-area surveys. The shortest wavelength (350 μ m) module (led by Canada) will perform a 860-GHz continuum survey, enabled by the very low precipitable water vapor at the CCAT-p site, which increases mapping speed by more than a factor of 4 over the ALMA plateau (Radford et al., 2016). Two further modules will make measurements in the 220-, 270-, 350- and 405-GHz bands simultaneously. One of these is matched to the atmospheric windows for optimal detection of continuum radiation, while the other one is equipped with a Fabry-Perot interferometer (FPI) for spectral imaging observations. Table 1 shows science goals with instrument modules and survey areas. The required areas and integration times are based on detailed science simulations that fold in the wavelength coverage, sensitivity and FoV of PCam (Figs. 1 and 2).

As a key example of the science, wide area multiwavelength CCAT-p surveys, enabled by the Canadian-led PCam350, will measure the dust-obscured star-formation properties of hundreds of thousands of galaxies out to $z \sim 5-7$ with high precision. This will greatly enhance our picture of cosmic galaxy evolution, probing 2-to-10 times lower luminosities than Herschel-SPIRE at $z > 2$ (due to source confusion; see insets of Fig. 1), while sampling large-scale environments (voids, the field, groups, and clusters) over two orders of magnitude larger areas than feasible to map with ALMA (the FoV of ALMA is a fraction of a single CCAT-p pixel). CCAT-p probes much deeper than Herschel-SPIRE, while sampling environments and luminosities inaccessible to ALMA surveys because of cosmic variance. Predicted reliability of far-infrared luminosity measurements (Fig. 1) highlights the

vast improvements with CCAT-p's 350- μm band and wide spectral coverage.

2.2 JCMT and the successor to SCUBA-2

In collaboration with international partners, a consortium of Canadian universities led by McMaster are proposing to build a new submillimetre camera for the JCMT (Fig. 3). This successor to SCUBA-2 will be completed and on sky in 3 years (2023), mapping stars and galaxies 20 times faster than the camera currently on the telescope. The wide-field mapping capabilities of this new camera will be a unique and powerful discovery instrument for at least 10 years. Scientific breakthroughs will include measuring the variable rate at which newly forming stars accrete material from their surrounding gas and mapping out the spatial clustering of young dusty galaxies in the early Universe. With full linear polarization capabilities, the camera will also produce incredible wide-field maps of polarized submillimetre emission that uniquely trace the structure and morphology of the magnetic fields. These magnetic fields are an important energy component in star-forming gas and are currently not constrained in modern models of star formation. The new camera will be a vital complement to the high-resolution capabilities of ALMA. Investment in the new camera will allow Canada to maintain its leadership role in SMM astronomy.

The submillimetre wavelength of 850 μm probed by the new JCMT camera traces the processes involved in the creation and birth of most objects in the Universe, from galaxies forming at great distances when the Universe was very young to the formation of new stars in the neighborhood of our own Sun. This wavelength targets the “sweet spot” of maximum sensitivity to distant galaxies along with an optimized match to the weather conditions at the JCMT. The 20-times-faster mapping speed of this new camera will enable a next generation of large surveys that will build on and expand the scientific research carried out with the JCMT. The proposed new camera will be the flagship instrument at the JCMT for the next decade.

3 Relevance to Canada

Canada has a legacy of over 30 years of national involvement in SMM facilities, beginning with the JCMT and including many other newer and more specialized facilities. All of the major Canadian university astronomy groups have members who have made use of SMM facilities. The many research directions that have followed from this access to the SMM has also been mirrored by involvement in developing the instrumental technologies that are required to enable the science. These technology developments have involved Canadian industries too.

Future Canadian involvement in the next large SMM observatory (e.g. a 25-m CCAT and/or a 50-m AtLAST) requires a continuing involvement in the modest-costing projects now underway (i.e. JCMT upgrades and CCAT-p). The large SMM community in Canada will benefit significantly by this instrumentation work, since this allows Canadians to continue at the initial planning and development stages for these future facilities.

4 Timeline

Both CCAT-p and JCMT upgrades are the subject of CFI proposals to be submitted in January 2020. CCAT-25 and AtLAST are not likely to begin construction before 2030, although there will be costs associated with the development of both in the years leading up to the start of construction.

5 Cost

The Canadian CCAT-p team is requesting \$4.4M from CFI, with an identical request to provincial agencies. The Canadian JCMT consortium is requesting \$0.8M from CFI for the new continuum camera, with an identical request to provincial agencies. Needed contributions for large (>25m aperture) “2030-SMM-facilities” will probably begin at the level of at least \$100k/yr in 2026 and increase to more than \$500k/yr in 2029. Ongoing involvement in other ground-based SMM facilities through the decade will require similar investments.

Table 1: CCAT-p Science Cases

Table 1: Overview of how the science cases map onto the detector array types and planned surveys.

Science cases ^a	Type ^b	Frequencies ^c (GHz)	Resolution (arcsec)	Detectors		Survey Areas ^d (deg ²)	
				type	#	pilot	full
SZ, CMB, SF	bb, pol	220, 270, 350, 405	53, 46, 39, 37	TES	8640	100	12,000 ^e
EoR, SZ	sp	220, 270, 350, 405	53, 46, 39, 37	TES	4320	4	17
SF	bb	860	14.3	KID	18,216	both	both

^a Science cases - SZ: Clusters, SZ, & Cosmology; CMB: CMB polarization; SF: Star Formation History; EoR: Intensity Mapping of Reionization

^b Array types - bb: broadband; sp: spectroscopic with spectral resolution of 280; pol: polarization sensitive

^c 90 and 150 GHz data from Advanced ACTPol and Simons Observatory will be available by agreement.

^d Areas for initial 400 hour and multi-year 4000 hour surveys. 860 GHz will be used with both survey types.

^e Over 400 deg² of the survey will be observed down to the source confusion limit for the SF survey.

6 Governance / Membership structure

The CCATp and JCMT facilities are open to any Canadian to pursue involvement. However, both have been led by consortia of about half a dozen universities in the past 10 years (on behalf of the Canadian communities) – those who have managed to secure small pockets of funding to continue involvement. Both have found funding through universities and even personal grants that are small individually, but together amount to well over \$1M. While CMB experiments are largely closed collaborations, Canadians with interest have easily found routes into these collaborations due to their specific skill sets, and instrument expertise (especially the readout technology in the labs of M. Halpern and M. Dobbs).

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

This WP has proposed that existing and upcoming single-dish SMM facilities play a crucial role in SMM science, complementing powerful interferometers like ALMA, but also generating their own self contained, transformative science cases that are not accessible to interferometers, and even pioneering new science areas (like JCMT: Transients Large Program). In terms of mapping speed and sensitivity, SMM single-dish experiments can match and even surpass ALMA. While CCATp represents a new frontier in short-wavelength SMM science, JCMT upgrades planned for the next years will ensure that JCMT will continue to enable fundamental scientific advances in the coming decade.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The main risks are clearly funding and personnel related. Single-dish SMM is not part of NRC's supported observatories at present, and Canada will lose access to these crucial facilities if it cannot maintain involvement through significant funding awards in the coming year.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Canadians have demonstrated significant scientific leadership with CCATp and JCMT (see Sections 1 and 2). The CCATp Canadian consortium (CATC) is led by M. Fich, and a major 350- μ m instrument for CCATp (PCam350) is a fully Canadian-led instrument (PI. S. Chapman). There will be opportunities for Canadian technical and strategic leadership in specific areas of JCMT and CCATp development over the next 10 years

Figure 1: **Prime-Cam** will enable exciting new measurements spanning an enormous range of cosmic times and scales, as shown on this schematic history of the Universe. **Top:** The four primary science surveys addressed by the proposed Prime-Cam observations include: intensity mapping of the epoch of reionization surveys (EoR, lower panels); galaxy cluster and Sunyaev-Zeldovich surveys (SZ); CMB polarization surveys (CMB); and dust-obscured star-formation history surveys (SF). These surveys will complement many existing and upcoming observations. **Middle:** EoR Survey – Simulated “redshift slice” (middle) of the area covered by the [CII] intensity-mapping survey in the epoch of reionization (EoR), representing a small spectral bin within the vast $z = 3.3\text{--}9.3$ redshift range covered by the Prime-Cam spectrometer [CII] measurements. The brightest of the sources in each pixel are those now detected in [CII] on an individual basis with ALMA (left), demonstrating that the line is typically one to two orders of magnitude brighter than CO in “normal” galaxies within the first billion years of cosmic time – and thus, much easier to detect. Besides the bright sources, Prime-Cam will also detect the aggregate [CII] emission from the highly numerous but individually faint reionization galaxies that are below the detection threshold of even ALMA and JWST. The entire field-of-view of ALMA is approximately 4 times smaller than each of the 6,000 Prime-Cam pixels, and its bandwidth is >30 times smaller than what is covered by the EoR survey. Prime-Cam will measure the clustering of star-forming galaxies at these redshifts (right), which determines the topology of cosmic reionization, through an analysis of the power spectrum of the [CII] emission (shown for $z = 6.5$). State-of-the-art model predictions (lines) differ by factors of 30–50. The full Prime-Cam survey will be sufficiently sensitive (shaded area) to differentiate between these predictions for the first time. **Bottom:** Star-formation survey, enabled largely by the Canadian-led 350- μm camera (see text).

Figure 2: The CCAT-p and Prime-Cam instrument (**Top**) **Site and telescope summary**. Left: The Cerro Chajnantor site offers the best submillimeter observing conditions of any well-characterized site, so that $350\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ surveys proceed 4 times faster than even at the ALMA site (top quartile pwv 0.28 vs. 0.53 mm at zenith). Centre: The CCAT-p telescope is being built by Vertex Antennentechnik and is scheduled for completion in 2021. Right: Mapping speed at 45° elevation for a camera with $1.5 \lambda/D$ -spaced horns that fills the FoV of a single optics tube in CCAT-p compared with an identical camera on other coeval telescopes. We make the comparison for intensity mapping referred to a $1'$ beam for the top two weather quartiles. Bottom centre table: Calculations include telescope site pwv at 1st and 2nd quartiles, telescope wave-front error, emissivity, and field of view (FoV). CCAT-p is > 30 times faster in all cases per optics tube. In principle, Prime-Cam can hold up to seven tubes. (**Bottom**) **Schematic of the telescope optics and Prime-Cam instrument**. The telescope and instrument module optics designs take advantage of mature technologies to provide diffraction-limited image quality across a wide FOV. This shows a preliminary design of the Prime-Cam instrument with the three instrument modules.

Figure 3: **A proposed new continuum camera for the JCMT.** Canada is aiming to be a partner in this instrument development, through a CFI proposal (PI: Wilson). **(Top left)** The optical design that puts the new MKID instrument into the JCMT Receiver cabin. **(Middle)** A possible design of the JCMT MKID instrument that can be adopted for both the JCMT receiver cabin and the Nasmyth platform. At the Nasmyth the optic axis would be horizontal as shown, whereas in the receiver cabin, the window would tilt upwards at approximately 50° when the antenna is pointed to zenith. **(Bottom)** Prototype LMT/ToI TEC 10 pixel 1.1-mm array. The layout of a single dual polarisation pixel (left) and an expanded view of the inductor/absorbers (right). The new JCMT MKID pixel will have a similar design optimised for $850\ \mu\text{m}$.

if funding can be secured.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

JCMT is clearly the premier instrument for sub-millimetre-wave single-dish astronomy at present. The high demand for time on JCMT by Canadians in the past 5 years (oversubscriptions consistently approaching 6:1, largely due to the limited amount of time available), and the increasing number of papers and projects led by Canadians (Section 2.2) are signs of our community's involvement, as are the large number of development studies and CFI proposals led by Canadians.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

The purpose of continued involvement in CCATp and JCMT is entirely to gain such opportunities in the coming decade. For example, in scientific results, student training, and technical and software development.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

Cost-benefit for all SMM single-dish experiments has been off-scale the past 10 years, as minimal cash, offset by the significant Canadian expertise and experience have allowed continued involvement. While larger amounts of funding are now required to push into the next decade, the cost-benefit will continue to be immense as the next generation facilities promise to transform science in innumerable ways.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

The single-dish SMM facilities and proposals are relatively large, international collaborations. There is acknowledged Canadian expertise, which has been sought out specifically for continued involvement in JCMT and CCATp, despite Canadian funding hurdles and shortfalls in these projects. However, in order to play leading roles in the future, it will be necessary to find the funding and resources to fulfill our partnership requirements. There is a serious risk Canada will be dropped from both projects if funding is not secured very soon.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

There are numerous opportunities for industry to be involved in the instrument development and fabrication for JCMT and CCATp, and beyond to the CMB-focused single-dish SMM facilities (POLARBEAR, SPT, Simons Observatory, and on to CMB-Stage 4). NRC and the universities both have excellent track records of attracting industrial subcontracts in such instrument developments. This ranges on scales from small NSERC-Engage programs at the \$25k level (PI: Chapman) to much larger engagements (PIs: Halpern; Dobbs). Another important aspect is HQP, but this requires funding support and commitment. Particularly critical is the support for postdoctoral researchers. There is currently no obvious source of support of this kind for a group of Canadians, of the sort that is readily available for our main international partners.

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